

Kamis , 28 Oktober 2021

Faizal Risdianto, IAIN Salatiga.

Editor in Chief REGISTER Journal, SINTA 2, terindeks di **ESCI WoS**.

IJIMS School of
Journal

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REGISTER JOURNAL

Indexed in

Clarivate
Analytics

Web of Science

REGISTER JOURNAL was published by [IAIN Salatiga](#), Central Java, Indonesia. It had been accredited SINTA 2 on 24th October 2018 by [RistekDikti of The Republic of Indonesia](#) as an achievement for the peer-reviewed journal, which has excellent quality in management and publication. The recognition was published in Director Decree [\(SK No. 30/E/KPT/2018\)](#) and is effective until 2021.

This journal was also successfully indexed at [CLARIVATE ANALYTICS](#) and [ACI \(ASEAN CITATION INDEX\)](#) in [April 2019](#). Emerging **Sources Citation Index (ESCI)** of **Web of Science** Master Journal List in June 2019.

MATERI HARI INI BISA DIUNDUH DI

[https://tinyurl.com/
RJISULTRAseries5](https://tinyurl.com/RJISULTRAseries5)

Rank by Journal Citation Indicator (JCI)

Journals within a category are sorted in descending order by Journal Citation Indicator (JCI) resulting in the Category Ranking below. A separate rank is shown for each category in which the journal is listed in JCR. Data for the most recent year is presented at the top of the list, with other years shown in reverse chronological order. [Learn more](#)

CATEGORY

EDUCATION & EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH

632/722

JCR YEAR	JCI RANK	JCI QUARTILE	JCI PERCENTILE	
2020	632/722	Q4	12.53	
2019	n/a	n/a	n/a	
2018	n/a	n/a	n/a	
2017	n/a	n/a	n/a	

CATEGORY

LINGUISTICS

242/259

JCR YEAR	JCI RANK	JCI QUARTILE	JCI PERCENTILE	
2020	242/259	Q4	6.76	
2019	n/a	n/a	n/a	
2018	n/a	n/a	n/a	
2017	n/a	n/a	n/a	

Journal Citation Report™ (JCR)

Journal Citation Reports™ 2021

Journal Citation Indicator (JCI)

NEW METRIC

The Journal Citation Indicator is a measure of the average Category Normalized Citation Impact (CNCI) of citable items (articles & reviews) published by a journal over a recent three year period. It is used to help you evaluate journals based on other metrics besides the Journal Impact Factor (JIF).

2020

0.13

Categories:

Education & Educational Research | Linguistics

2019

0.15

Categories:

Education & Educational Research | Linguistics

[Learn About Journal Citation Indicator](#)

Feedback

INTERMESO: HARGA JURNAL ESCI WOS

MENGENAL LEBIH JAUH CLARIVATE-WOS

Clarivate
Analytics

WEB OF SCIENCE™

SEJARAH CLARIVATE ANALYTICS-WOS

1960: Dr. Eugene Garfield mendirikan ISI –**Institute for Scientific Information** di Philadelphia. ISI offered scientometric and bibliographic database services. Its specialty was citation indexing and analysis.

1964 Dr. Garfield mengenalkan **SCI-Science Citation Index**.

1992 – ISI dibeli oleh **Thomson-Reuters** menjadi **ISI THOMSON**

1997 Nama ISI diubah menjadi **WEB OF SCIENCE**

SEJARAH **CLARIVATE ANALYTICS-WOS**

2001 WOS punya database baru, WEB OF KNOWLEDGE

2016 THOMSON REUTERS Menjual **intellectual property** kepada CLARIVATE ANALYTICS

2017 CLARIVATE mengakuisisi PUBLON, database untuk reviewers

2018 CLARIVATE ANALYTICS meluncurkan produk bernama KOPERNIO, browser extension yang utk pencarian publikasi full text (pdf) database jurnal seperti google scholar, pubmed dst...

INDONESIAN JOURNAL OF ISLAM AND MUSLIM SOCIETIES

INDONESIAN JOURNAL OF ISLAM AND MUSLIM SOCIETIES

OPEN ACCESS

Publisher: INST AGAMA ISLAM NEGERI-IAIN SALATIGA , JL TENTARA PELAJAR NO 2, SALATIGA, JAWA TENGAH, INDONESIA, 50721

ISSN / eISSN: 2089-1490 / 2406-825X

Web of Science Core Collection: Emerging Sources Citation Index

 Share This Journal

View profile page

** Requires free login.*

REGISTER JOURNAL

Exact Match Found

REGISTER JOURNAL

OPEN ACCESS

Publisher: STATE INST ISLAMIC STUDIES SALATIGA, TEACHER TRAINING & EDUC FAC , JL LINGKAR SALATIGA KM 02, PULUTAN, SIDOREJO, CENTRAL JAVA, SALATIGA, INDONESIA, 50716

ISSN / eISSN: 1979-8903 / 2503-040X

Web of Science Core Collection: Emerging Sources Citation Index

 Share This Journal

View profile page

** Requires free login.*

History of Web of Science

1964

- Garfield Introduces the first **Science Citation Index**
- A five-volume print edition indexing 613 journals and 1.4 million citations

1966

- The **Science Citation Index** becomes available on magnetic tape

1988

- **Science Citation Index** becomes available on CR-ROM

1997

- Science Citation Index becomes part of a web environment named **Web of Science**

2014

- The Web of Knowledge is redesigned being given its current name **Web of Science Core Collection**

2017

- Clarivate Analytics acquires Publons, creator of the leading online global peer-review platform

1965

- Dr. Garfield introduces the **Journal Impact Factor**, a metric to measure the impact of a journal

1975

- Commercial appearance of the Journal Impact Factor on **Journal Citation Reports (JCR)**

1992

- **ISI** is acquired by Thomson, who later merged with Reuters in 2008 to operate as Thomson Reuters

2001

- Web of Science is incorporated to other databases into a platform names **Web of Knowledge**

2016

- Thomson Reuters sold the Intellectual Property and Science (IP&S) business and from this separation merged an independent company, **Clarivate Analytics**

2018

- Clarivate Analytics acquired **Kopernio**, an A.I. technology business that revolutionises how researchers access articles across the globe

MENGENAL WEB OF SCIENCE

Web of Science (sebelumnya dikenal sebagai Web of Knowledge) adalah layanan pengindeksan sitiran ilmiah berbasis langganan daring. Web of Science (WoS) adalah salah satu database rujukan global terbesar dan paling terkemuka.

THOMSON REUTERS

Clarivate
Analytics

WEB OF SCIENCE™

MENGENAL WEB OF SCIENCE

Web of Science “*stronger in Humanities than Scopus*” (lebih kuat dalam bidang Humaniora). Salah satu turunan produk Clarivate Analytics adalah Publons, yang dapat dimanfaatkan secara gratis oleh pengelola jurnal ilmiah guna mencari mitra bestari (*scientific journal reviewer*) berdasarkan riwayat dan *merit system*.

BEBERAPA INDEX DALAM *WEB OF SCIENCE* (WOS)

Journals

- **Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE)**: clinical, natural and applied sciences
- **Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI)**: social sciences
- **Arts & Humanities Citation Index (AHCI)**: arts and humanities
- **Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI)**: all disciplines

Books

- **Book Citation Index (BKCI)**: all disciplines

Conference proceedings

- **Conference Proceedings Citation Index (CPCI)**: all disciplines

Web of Science Core Collection

Pengalaman mengelola jurnal terindeks di ESCI Web of Science cukup menarik bagi saya.

Di satu sisi, ada orang yang berpendapat ESCI WoS itu adalah sekadar indexing kelas menengah sejenis DOAJ, EBSCO, ACI bahkan ada yang bilang ESCI WoS itu **indexing setengah hati** yang **belum masuk** core collections Web of Science. Core collection dalam konteks ini adalah produk web of Science yang masuk indexing kelas tinggi yaitu SSCI, SCIE dan AHCI.

Di sisi yang lain sejatinya **ESCI sudah masuk core collection** tapi belum punya Impact Factor dan setidaknya ada Point positif jika sebuah jurnal terindeks di ESCI Web of Science:

ESCI Web of Science adalah jalan lain untuk internasionalisasi jurnal. Bagi pengelola jurnal yang masih **belum berani** mendaftarkan jurnal ke Scopus/mungkin **sudah mendaftar tapi kena embargo**. Internasionalisasi jurnal maksudnya akan banyak peminat dari Foreign authors seperti: Turki, Rusia, Pakistan, Iran, Thailand, Malaysia yang tertarik dan menganggap tinggi produk apapun dari WoS meskipun **sekadar** ESCI WoS.

Dr. Mila Cahue, Head of Editorial Outreach WoS
mengatakan bahwa jika sebuah jurnal ada di ESCI ini
adalah tahapan awal sebuah jurnal terindeks di Web
of Science, the world's most trusted global citation
database and the most powerful research engine,
delivering your library with best-in-class publication
and citation data.

THE QUALITY OF JOURNAL CONTENT IS THE KING

Fakta yang unik ialah pada acara ***Web of Science Selection Criteria & Evaluation Process Workshop*** di Surabaya, Agustus 2019 diungkapkan oleh Prof Komang G. Wiryawan dari ***Tropical Animal Science Journal***, IPB, Bogor bahwa dalam kurun waktu 3 tahun ada 80-an jurnal Indonesia yang telah ada di ESCI WOS tapi belum ada yang naik level ke SSCI, SCIE dan AHCI padahal banyaknya diantaranya yang sudah di Scopus. Jawaban Dr. Mila Cahue sebagai representative WOS. ***It is like New York Marathon. Thousand of people joining the marathon but only few people win the game.*** Intinya WOS sangat menekankan kualitas jurnal dan artikelnya.

4 BASIC REQUIREMENT FOR CLARIVATE

[HTTPS://MJL.CLARIVATE.COM/WOS-JOURNAL-SUBMISSION/WOS-JOURNAL-SUBMISSION.HTML](https://mjl.clarivate.com/wos-journal-submission/wos-journal-submission.html)

Electronic Journal Submission

Clarivate Analytics evaluates journals that meet the following minimum criteria:

1. The journal publishes peer reviewed content.
2. The journal has an ISSN registered with the ISSN International Centre. For more information, visit the [ISSN International Centre](#).
3. **The journal should include English language bibliographic information, including Titles, Abstracts, Keywords and Cited references.**
4. The journal should include references in Roman script.

Tutorial dan link web <https://bit.ly/daftarkeESCIwos>

24 PERSYARATAN LENGKAP REGISTER KE WOS

1. **ISSN** :Jurnal harus memiliki ISSN
2. **Judul Jurnal**: Jurnal harus memiliki judul yang khas & sesuai dengan ISSN
3. **Penerbit Jurnal**: Nama penerbit harus dinyatakan dengan jelas
4. **URL Jurnal**: Jika ada versi online, wajib untuk menyebutkan alamat URL jurnal
5. **Akses Konten**: Tim editorial WoS harus punya akses penuh ke konten yang dipublikasikan
6. **Kebijakan Peer Review**: Jurnal harus memberikan pernyataan yang mudah diakses & jelas tentang komitmennya terhadap tinjauan sejawat (Peer Review)

-
7. **Rincian Kontak:** Rincian kontak untuk peran editorial & produksi jurnal harus disediakan
 8. **Konten Ilmiah:** Jurnal harus berisi konten yang bersifat ilmiah dan asli.
 9. **Judul Artikel dan Abstrak Artikel dalam Bahasa Inggris.** Terlepas dari bahasa dalam full text articles, jurnal harus menyediakan terjemahan bahasa Inggris yang akurat.
 10. **Informasi Bibliografi dalam Roman Script:** Referensi, nama, & afiliasi yang dikutip harus dalam aksara Romawi
 11. **Kejelasan Bahasa:** Jjudul, abstrak, dan semua teks publikasi lainnya yang disajikan dalam bahasa Inggris.
 12. **Ketepatan Waktu Publikasi:** Jurnal harus menyatakan apakah memiliki frekuensi publikasi yang ditentukan.

13. **Fungsionalitas Situs Web/Format Jurnal**: Informasi situs web harus akurat, rancangan informasi & sistem navigasi situs web harus dipastikan aksesnya mudah ke konten yang diterbitkan.

14. **Kehadiran Pernyataan Etika**: Jurnal harus transparan mengenai persyaratan etika untuk penulis dan karya yang diterbitkan.

15. **Detail Afiliasi Editorial**: Anggota Dewan Editorial harus dapat diidentifikasi & siap dihubungi.

16. **Detail Afiliasi Penulis**: Penulis semua karya ilmiah harus diidentifikasi secara akurat.

17. **Komposisi Dewan Redaksi**: Afiliasi Editor & Anggota Dewan Editorial, keragaman geografis, dan catatan publikasi harus konsisten dengan ruang lingkup yang dinyatakan dalam konten jurnal.

18. **Validitas Pernyataan:** Konten yang dipublikasikan harus menunjukkan kepatuhan terhadap kebijakan yang dinyatakan oleh jurnal.

19. **Tinjauan Sejawat:** Konten yang dipublikasikan harus mencerminkan tinjauan sejawat dan/atau pengawasan editorial yang memadai dan efektif.

20. **Relevansi Konten:** Konten yang diterbitkan harus konsisten dengan judul dan ruang lingkup jurnal yang dinyatakan.

21. **Detail Dukungan Hibah.**

22. **Kepatuhan pada Standar Komunitas:** Kebijakan editorial harus konsisten dengan praktik terbaik bonafid seperti standar COPE

23. **Distribusi Penulis:** Penulis harus memiliki afiliasi, keragaman geografis, dan catatan publikasi yang memvalidasi partisipasi mereka dalam komunitas ilmiah yang terkait.

24. **Kutipan yang Sesuai untuk Referensi:** Diharapkan bahwa artikel tepat mengambil kutipan referensi yang menjadi cakupan untuk topik penulisan.

THE JOURNAL EVALUATION PROCESS FOR THE WEB OF SCIENCE CORE COLLECTION

1. Initial Triage**2. Editorial Triage****3. Editorial Evaluation****Quality Criteria****Impact Criteria**

- ✓ ISSN
- ✓ Journal Title
- ✓ Journal Publisher
- ✓ URL (online journals)
- ✓ Content Access
- ✓ Presence of Peer Review Policy
- ✓ Contact Details

- ✓ Scholarly Content
- ✓ Article Titles and Article Abstracts in English
- ✓ Bibliographic Information in Roman Script
- ✓ Clarity of Language
- ✓ Timeliness and/or Publication Volume
- ✓ Website Functionality/Journal Format
- ✓ Presence of Ethics Statements
- ✓ Editorial Affiliation Details
- ✓ Author Affiliation Details

- ✓ Editorial Board Composition
- ✓ Validity of Statements
- ✓ Peer Review
- ✓ Content Relevance
- ✓ Grant Support Details
- ✓ Adherence to Community Standards
- ✓ Author Distribution
- ✓ Appropriate Citations to the Literature

- ✓ Comparative Citation Analysis
- ✓ Author Citation Analysis
- ✓ EBM Citation Analysis
- ✓ Content Significance

Successful outcomes

Starts editorial triage

Starts editorial evaluation

Enters ESCI and is evaluated for impact

Enters SCIE/SSCI/AHCI

Unsuccessful outcomes**Failed initial triage**

Re-submission welcome as soon as issues have been resolved

Failed editorial triage

Re-submission welcome as soon as issues have been resolved

Failed editorial quality evaluation

Re-submission subject to embargo of at least two years

Failed editorial impact evaluation

Entry/continued coverage in ESCI

Re-evaluation subject to embargo of at least two years

THE INITIAL TRIAGE

Triage awal dilakukan menggunakan informasi yang disediakan oleh penerbit. Tujuan utama dari langkah triase ini adalah:

- Untuk memastikan identifikasi yang jelas dari jurnal yang diajukan evaluasi
- Untuk memastikan kami memiliki akses teks penuh ke konten
- Untuk mengetahui kebijakan peer review jurnal
- Untuk mengetahui siapa yang harus dihubungi jika kami memiliki pertanyaan atau masalah

Jika informasi yang diperlukan tidak disediakan, Editor Web of Science tidak dapat melanjutkan dengan evaluasi. Tidak ada periode embargo untuk pengiriman ulang jika jurnal tidak lolos triase awal.

Enter tracking number
13D401898D768 Submit

Indonesian Journal of Islam and Muslim Societies (2089-1490 / 2406-825X)

Submission Received
29-Apr-2018

Validated

Enrichment in progress

Enrichment completed

Ready to be released to CSAB

Under review by the CSAB

Review complete
Accepted
13-Aug-2017

VS.

WEB OF SCIENCE™

Secara marketing Scopus lebih user friendly karena terdapat suggestor step yang jelas kapan diterima dan kapan keputusan utk accepted or rejected. sedangkan WoS can only be reached via E-mail correspondence.

Enter tracking number
13D401898D768 Submit

Indonesian Journal of Islam and Muslim Societies (2089-1490 / 2406-825X)

Submission Received
29-Apr-2018

Validated

Enrichment in progress

Enrichment completed

Ready to be released to CSAB

Under review by the CSAB

Review complete
Accepted
13-Aug-2017

VS.

WEB OF SCIENCE™

Herman, Lauren <lauren.herman@clarivate.com>

to me ▾

Dear Faizal,

The journal was accepted into ESCI as of June 2019. It does not appear the acceptance letter has been sent yet

Best regards,
Lauren

Lauren Herman

Publisher Relations Liaison

Web of Science Group | **Clarivate Analytics**

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1500 Spring Garden Street, 4th Floor | Philadelphia, PA | USA

clarivate.com/publisher-relations

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HTTP://MJL.CLARIVATE.COM/CGI-BIN/JRNLST/JLRESULTS.CGI?PC=EX&FULL=*REGISTER%20JOURNAL

mjl.clarivate.com/cgi-bin/jrnlst/jlresults.cgi?PC=EX&Full=*Register journal

Search Term(s): *REGISTER JOURNAL · The following title(s) matched your request

1-1 of 1 journals

Format for print

REGISTER JOURNAL

Semiannual
ISSN: 1979-8903
E-ISSN: 2503-040X
STATE INST ISLAMIC STUDIES SALATIGA, TEACHER TRAINING & EDUC FAC, JL LINGKAR
SALATIGA KM 02, PULUTAN, SIDOREJO, CENTRAL JAVA, SALATIGA, INDONESIA, 50716
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Category

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Search

Sort By: Title (A-Z)

Found 1 results (Page 1)

REGISTER JOURNAL OPEN ACCESS (Exact Match)

Publisher: STATE INST ISLAMIC STUDIES SALATIGA, TEACHER TRAINING & EDUC FAC, JL LINGKAR SALATIGA KM 02, PULUTAN, SIDOREJO, CENTRAL JAVA, SALATIGA, INDONESIA, 50716

ISSN / eISSN: 1979-8903 / 2503-040X

Categories: LINGUISTICS | SOCIAL SCIENCES, GENERAL | EDUCATION & EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH

Web of Science Core Collection: Emerging Sources Citation Index

[View profile page](#)

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(most recent 20)

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NAME: (REGISTER JOURNAL)

Timespan: All years. Indexes: ESCI, CPCI-SSH, SCI-EXPANDED, DCI-S, SSCI, BKCI-SSH, A&HCI, DCI-SSH, CPCI-S, BKCI-S.

[...Less](#)

◀ 1 of 2 ▶

Select Page

1. **Utilization of Edmodo as an Online Tool in EFL Writing Class to Increase Students' Writing Ability**

By: Miftah, M. Zaini

REGISTER JOURNAL Volume: 11 Issue: 1 Pages: 37-58 Published: 2018

Usage Count: 0 (Last 180 Days) 0 (Since 2013)

[View Abstract](#)

Times Cited: 0

(from Web of Science Core Collection)

2. **Developing Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) : Need Analysis of Teaching Materials for Madrasah English Teachers**

By: Mustikasari, Dewi Wahyu

REGISTER JOURNAL Volume: 10 Issue: 2 Pages: 170-184 Published: 2017

Usage Count: 0 (Last 180 Days) 0 (Since 2013)

[View Abstract](#)

Times Cited: 0

(from Web of Science Core Collection)

3. **Trick of Political Identity: Analyzing Appraisal System on 212 Movement Reunion in Online Media**

By: Gunawan, Fahmi, Thahara, Yoni, Risdianto, Faizal

Times Cited: 0

(from Web of Science Core Collection)

BRIDGING THE GAPS TOWARD REPUTABLE INTERNATIONAL JOURNALS

CONTOH JURNAL YANG ADA DI ESCI WOS

Search Results

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IJOLE-INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF LANGUAGE EDUCATION

OPEN ACCESS

Publisher: UNIV NEGERI MAKASSAR, FAC LANGUAGES & LITERATURE, KAMPUS FBS UNM PARANG TAMBUNG, JL DAENG TATA RAYA MAKASSAR, MAKASSAR, INDONESIA, 90224

ISSN / eISSN: 2548-8457 / 2548-8465

Categories: EDUCATION & EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH | SOCIAL SCIENCES, GENERAL | LINGUISTICS

Web of Science Core Collection: Emerging Sources Citation Index

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Home > Vol 17, No 1 (2021)

Jurnal Pendidikan Fisika Indonesia

Jurnal Pendidikan Fisika Indonesia [p-ISSN 1693-1246 | e-ISSN 2355-3812] is a peer-reviewed journal published two times a year (January and July) by Department of Physics, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Universitas Negeri Semarang. Jurnal Pendidikan Fisika Indonesia is an integrated forum for communicating scientific advances in the field of physics and education physics. The journal reports significant new findings related to physics and education physics, including: learning media development, learning methods development, learning methods implementation and several application of physics.

Jurnal Pendidikan Fisika Indonesia publishes comprehensive research articles and invited reviews by leading expert in the field. Papers will be selected that high scientific merit, impart important new knowledge, and are of high interest to physics and education physics community. Jurnal Pendidikan Fisika Indonesia has become a CrossRef member with DOI prefix: 10.15294/jpfi. Therefore, all articles published by the journal have unique DOI number.

This Journal is firstly published in 2003 and periodically published twice per year. Since 2011 it is accredited with quality level achievement of B by Directorate General of Higher Education, Ministry of Education and Culture, Republic of Indonesia No. 81/DIKTI/Kep./2011, Ministry of Research, Technology, and Higher Education, Republic Indonesia with Second Grade (Peringkat 2, Sinta 2) since year 2016 to 2020 according to the decree No. 21/E/KPT/2018 & Ministry of Research and Technology/National Agency for Research and Innovation 2020-2024, Number 148/M/KPT/2020

Jurnal Pendidikan Fisika Indonesia is indexed in Emerging Sources Citation Index (Clarivate Analytics), Directory of Open Access Journals, Google Scholar, GARUDA, Crossref DOI, EBSCO Open Science Directory, SINTA 2

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 **Clarivate
Analytics**

**EMERGING SOURCES
CITATION INDEX**

EDITORIAL TRIAGE

Pada langkah ini, Editor Web of Science meninjau jurnal untuk menentukan apakah evaluasi editorial lengkap pantas untuk dilakukan.

Karakteristik jurnal yang akan dievaluasi meliputi:

- Apakah jurnal mengandung sejumlah besar konten ilmiah
- Apakah persyaratan bahasa Inggris / skrip Romawi terpenuhi
- Apakah artikel ditulis dengan cara yang jelas dan mudah dipahami
- Apakah jurnal mempublikasikan volume konten yang menunjukkan minat kepada komunitas riset yang dituju
- Adanya detail editorial dan afiliasi penulis untuk memungkinkan identifikasi yang benar. Tidak ada periode embargo untuk pengiriman ulang jika jurnal tidak lolos triase editorial.

EDITORIAL EVALUATION/THE QUALITY

Dalam langkah ini, Editor Web of Science sedang memeriksa untuk menyelaraskan antara judul jurnal, scope yang dinyatakan, komposisi dewan editorial dan konten yang diterbitkan. Mereka juga mencari bukti ketegasan editorial dan kepatuhan terhadap standar komunitas.

Karakteristik jurnal yang akan dievaluasi meliputi:

- Apakah konten yang diterbitkan konsisten dengan judul jurnal dan ruang lingkup yang dinyatakan
- Apakah kapasitas dan keahlian dewan editorial sesuai dengan volume dan luasnya konten yang diterbitkan
- Apakah ada bukti peer review yang kuat
- Apakah penulis menunjukkan karakteristik yang memvalidasi partisipasi mereka dalam komunitas ilmiah yang relevan
- Apakah literatur di sekitarnya dikutip dengan tepat

Jika jurnal tidak lulus langkah ini, pengajuan kembali dikenakan embargo paling tidak dua tahun.

EDITORIAL EVALUATION/ IMPACT

Kriteria dalam langkah ini dirancang untuk memilih jurnal yang paling berdampak di bidang penelitian tertentu, menggunakan aktivitas kutipan sebagai indikator utama untuk mengetahui faktor dampak

Analisis kutipan dilakukan di:

➤ Tingkat jurnal, ➤ Tingkat penulis, ➤ Tingkat Dewan Editorial

Ada faktor tambahan yang dipertimbangkan:

➤ Konten dalam jurnal harus menarik, penting, dan bernilai bagi pembaca yang dituju dan pelanggan Web of Science

➤ Signifikansi konten dapat dibuktikan sebagai spesialisasi yang unik, perspektif novel, fokus regional atau konten yang tidak biasa yang memperkaya luasnya cakupan Web of Science.

Atribut-atribut ini tidak secara eksklusif tercermin dalam aktivitas kutipan tingkat jurnal.

Jika jurnal tidak lulus langkah ini, evaluasi ulang akan dikenakan periode embargo setidaknya dua tahun.

ESCI WOS INDEXED
BUT THEY ARE NOT HAVING FULL TEXT IN ENGLISH

Journal of Qualitative Research in Education, Práxis Educacional
TEXTO LIVRE-LINGUAGEM E TECNOLOGIA

Jurnal-jurnal ini fulltext bukan dalam Bahasa Inggris, namun **has English language bibliographic information**. Jurnal sudah mencakup informasi bibliografi bahasa Inggris, termasuk Judul, Abstrak, Kata Kunci dan referensi yang dikutip.

DOSSIÊ TEMÁTICO: Formação Docente, Práticas Pedagógicas e Relações Raciais e de Gênero

 <https://doi.org/10.22481/praxisedu.v16i39.6358>

**DEZ ANOS DA LEI N. 10.639/2003 E A FORMAÇÃO DE PROFESSORES E
RELAÇÕES RACIAIS¹ EM ARTIGOS (2003/2013): UM TEMA EM DISCUSSÃO**

TEN YEARS OF STATURE N. 10.639 / 2003 AND TEACHERS 'TRAINING AND
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AÚN EN DISCUSIÓN

İlkokul Birinci Sınıf Çocuklarının Velisi Olmak: Heyecan ve Endişeyi Dengeleyebilmek*

Being Parents of First Graders in Primary School: Balancing the Excitement and Anxiety

Zuhal Çeliktürk Sezgin**

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Çeliktürk Sezgin, Z. (2020). İlkokul birinci sınıf çocuklarının velisi olmak: Heyecan ve endişeyi dengeleyebilmek. *Eğitimde Nitel Araştırmalar Dergisi – Journal of Qualitative Research in Education*, 8(1), 1-17. doi:10.14689/issn.2148-2624.1.8c.1s.1m

Öz. Bu çalışmanın amacı, öğrenci velilerinin ilkokul birinci sınıf velisi olma deneyimlerini anlamaktır. Çalışmada temel nitel araştırma yaklaşımı benimsenmiştir. Araştırmanın katılımcılarını 10 öğrenci velisi oluşturmaktadır. Veriler yarı yapılandırılmış görüşme ve doküman analizleriyle değerlendirilmiştir. Çalışmalar, 2018 Eylül-Mart aylarında gerçekleştirilmiştir.

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